

The Impact of Job Insecurity and Job Stress on Turnover Intention by Digital Transformation as a Moderating Variable at PT. ABC Airport, Yogyakarta Branch Office

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ABSTRACT: This study does get the objective to explore the impact of job insecurity and job stress on turnover intention, by digital transformation serving as a moderating variable at PT. ABC Airport Yogyakarta Branch Office. A quantitative descriptive study design was employed, targeting 69 outsourced workers from the Yogyakarta branch. The sampling method utilized was a saturated sampling technique. Information collection was figured out by means of a survey, utilizing a questionnaire as the study instrument. information analysis was had utilizing the Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach by Partial Least Square (PLS). The findings reveal that job insecurity goodly and noteworthy impacts turnover intention. Similarly, job stress also indicates a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention. Additionally, digital transformation noteworthy moderates the unfavorable connection among job insecurity and turnover intention, as well as the good connection among job stress and turnover intention.

KEYWORDS: Digital transformation, Job insecurity, Job stress, Turnover intention.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization is broadening market access and linking businesses by consumers worldwide. This creates noteworthy opportunities for bussiness to grow their operations, but it also introduces new challenges in the form of heightened competition. As a outcome, bussiness are compelled to impactively manage a workforce that is skilled, competent, and capable to achieve optimal outcomes. However, in the process of managing its human resources, every company will face a phenomenon that is difficult to avoid, namely the exit of workers (turnover). The circumstance of turnover starts by the urgency of a desire to modify jobs (turnover intention) by workers. Turnover intention is basically only limited to the desire or intention of workers to leave the company, not to realize it. (Ardan, M., & Jaelani, 2021)..

The Yogyakarta branch of PT ABC Airport does get been facing a notable downturn in financial performance. This decline does get been largely attributed to the impact of the pandemic and the operational restrictions imposed on airports in compliance by regulatory guidelines. One of the policies regarded to cost reduction as an effort to survive the company is by no longer extending contracts for some outsourced workers (involuntary turnover) based on assessments. This condition was also followed by several outsourced workers who resigned (voluntary turnover). Table 1 below indicates information on the voluntary turnover rate of outsourced workers at the PT ABC Airport Yogyakarta branch from 2020 to 2023.

Table 1. Voluntary turnover rate of outsourced workers

	2020	2021	2022	2023
Turnover Rate	2,20 %	3,90 %	4,83 %	2,81%

Based on the information on top of, the number of resignations of outsourced workers is relatively low, but what needs to be a concern is when resignations are made by personnel who get previously passed an assessment or performance evaluation. Evaluation is a key step in identifying top talent, but if these individuals choose to leave the company for various reasons, it outcomes in the loss of valuable and skilled human resources. Moreover, there are several units where the number of personnel, both permanent workers and outsourced workers, cumulatively still does not meet the standards set by the regulator. The area of work coverage at the airport does get not decreased so that this turnover phenomenon will increase the workload of personnel who are still working and does get the potential to become a demotivating factor for other support personnel that leads to job insecurity and job stress.

Any risk associated by employment for economic downturns and durations of financial uncertainty such that business lay off workers to decrease costs, can be said to be the uncertainty of future employment. (Getahun Asfaw & Chang, 2019). In particular, contract workers tend to get greater job insecurity than permanent workers (Klandermans et al., 2019). (Klandermans et al., 2010).. The workload delegated by personnel who decide to quit can also be one of the stressors for other workers who are still working today. Job stress that causes excessive tension on workers' emotions can affect a person at work (Akdon, 2017). (Akdon, 2017).

Conversely, the COVID-19 pandemic does get increased digital transformation across all sectors. The acceptance of digital transformation leads to the creation of a new work environment that is both more innovative and increasingly complex (Legner et al., 2017). This also does get an impact on human resources and the work environment that will get a direct impact on the psychological condition of workers and cause stress for workers if a company is too demanding for workers to keep up by the times and the absence of a transformation strategy that serves as a guide for organizations to achieve successful and sustainable transformation in the midst of an ever-changing business environment due to the development of digital technology. The greater the stage of job insecurity and stress, the greater the desire to quit work (Asdilvira et al., 2023).

Some previous studies get indicated inconsistencies among the connection among job insecurity and job stress on turnover intention. Such as study had by Arnes et al. (2020), Asdilvira et al. (2023) and Maulana et al. (2024) indicated that job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention, whereas Azizah & Murniningsih (2022) indicated that job insecurity does get a unfavorable and innoteworthy impact on turnover intention, while Suwarsono et al. Suwarsono et al. (2022) by the study outcomes that job insecurity does get a noteworthy unfavorable impact on turnover intention. Previous study on the impact of job stress on turnover intention was also discussed by Asdilvira et al. (2023) and Maulana et al. (2024) by the conclusion that job stress does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention. However, in contrast to study had by Ariansyah (2019) and Anastasia et al. (2022) who found that job stress does get a noteworthy unfavorable impact on turnover intention. Previous study regarded to the impact of digital transformation on job insecurity, job stress and turnover intention was discussed partially as in study had by Dengler & Gundert (2021), Makowska-Tłomak et al. (2023) and Caselli et al. (2023) that then in this study will test the impact of digital transformation as a moderating variable on the connection among job insecurity and job stress on turnover intention.

Based on the existing phenomenon gap and study gap, the studyer will assess the impact of job insecurity and job stress on the turnover intention of outsourced workers who are still working at the PT ABC Airport branch in Yogyakarta. In addition, this study will also analyze the moderating role of digital transformation variables on job stress and job insecurity for outsourced workers at the company.

HYPHOTESIS FORMULATION

1. Impact of Job Insecurity on Turnover intention

Job insecurity reflects the extent to that workers get their jobs are threatened and get powerless to do anything to keep their jobs (Hvinden et al., 2019). Job insecurity affects the increase in turnover where workers think about leaving work because they get high job insecurity. This is handled by the theory expressed by Heaney et al. (1994) that defines job insecurity as an individual's view of the potential threat to the continuity of his current job. Based on the outcomes of study had by Arnes et al. (2020) on outsourced workers at PT X indicates that job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention variables and is handled by study had by Asdilvira et al. Asdilvira et al. (2023) on workers of PT XYZ Aviation in Medan that indicates that job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on intention to stop working.

H1: Job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention.

2. Impact of Job Stress on Turnover intention

Work stress is an evolving state in that an individual confronts opportunities, demands, or resources that are interconnected by external environmental conditions, organizational frameworks, and intrinsic personal factors (Robbins et al., 2017).. As outlined by Robbins (2014), stress affects worker behavior in several noteworthy ways, including fluctuations in productivity, increased rates of worker turnover, greater stages of absenteeism, and a rise in workplace accidents. This is handled by study had by Asdilvira et al. (2023) on workers of PT XYZ Aviation in Medan that indicates that job stress does get a good and noteworthy impact on intention to stop working and study by Maulana et al. Maulana et al. (2024) by study outcomes indicateing that job stress does get a noteworthy good impact on turnover intention.

H2 : Job stress does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention.

3. The impact of Digital Transformation on the connection among Job Insecurity and Turnover Intention

Digital transformation can be explained as the strategic acceptance and integration of advanced digital technologies—including virtualization, mobile computing, cloud computing, and comprehensive system integration—to facilitate and drive organizational modify and innovation. (Loonam et al., 2018). Technological advancements present both opportunities and challenges for the traditional workforce. Workers may regard digitalization as a potential threat to their future employment and financial stability. Furthermore, the capabilities of digital tools to replicate specific human functions and tasks exacerbate concerns about their impact on human labor (Jarrahi, 2018)As a outcome, workers perceive digital transformation as a potential threat, leading to increased getings of job insecurity. This is handled by study (Çelik, 2024) that states that digital transformation does get a noteworthy good impact on job insecurity.

H3 : Digital Transformation moderates the noteworthy good connection among job insecurity and turnover Intention.

4. The impact of Digital Transformation on the connection among Job Stress and Turnover Intention

The increased expansion of the aviation sector, coupled by the rising influx of passengers, presents a formidable challenge for airports. They are tasked by optimizing operational efficiency, refining processes to curtail expenditures, enhancing passenger comfort, and upholding stringent safety standards (Kováčiková et al., 2022). In response to these demands, airports are increasingly embracing digital solutions to advance and refine their operations. Nonetheless, there is growing recognition of the adverse impact of digital transformation on workers' mental well-being. This includes the elevated stress outcomeing from the swift integration of digital technologies and the organizational shifts accompanying these modifys. (Hu X. et al., 2021). High job stress can unfavorably impact productivity, well-being, and overall organizational performance. This is handled by study Makowska-Tłomak et al. (2023) that indicates that stress due to digital transformation is noteworthyly greater among workers who are running digital solution projects in the workplace.

H4 : Digital Transformation moderates the noteworthy good connection among job stress and turnover intention.

Figure 1. Framework

METHOD

In this study the authors used quantitative study methods. The objective of the study is to decide the impact of job insecurity and job stress (independent variable) on turnover intention (dependent variable) by the moderating variable used is digital transformation. The study was had at PT ABC Airport’s Yogyakarta Branch Office. The population decided was all outsourced workers of PT ABC Airport’s Yogyakarta Branch Office by a saturated sample of 69 people.

Information collection involved administering questionnaires directly to participants, that were structured into two main segments. The first segment solicited demographic information, encompassing variables such as gender, age, educational attainment, and tenure. The second segment was dedicated to capturing study indicators pertinent to each variable under investigation.

The analysis of information was executed utilizing SmartPLS 4.1. This study incorporated a range of analytical procedures to test the hypotheses, that comprised evaluations of both the outer and inner models. The outer model assessment involved rigorous testing of construct validity and reliability. Validity test is measured utilizing Convergent Validity by looking at the loading factor

value > 0.7 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.5, while Discriminant Validity by the Fornell-Larcker Criterion test where the correlation value among variables by the variable itself must be greater than the correlation by other variables in the same construct, Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) by HTMT value on each variable less than 0.9 and cross loading value > 0.7. Reliability Test is measured by means of Cronbach's Alpha by a value > 0.7 and a Composite Reliability value > 0.7.

Inner model analysis includes R Square, Q Square, model fit and hypothesis testing. The R Square metric ranges from 0 to 1, where a value of 1 implies that the independent variable can entirely forecast the dependent variable devoid of error. Conversely, for Q Square values, any good value is deemed acceptable. In this study, the model's fit is evaluated based on the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), that is measured inside of the interval of 0.06 to 0.100. Hypothesis testing is done by means of Path coefficients bootstrapping where the original sample value is used to see the direction of hypothesis testing, t statistic value > 1.96, and P Value < 0.05.

RESULT

Description of Respondents

The study involved distributing questionnaires to all 69 outsourced workers currently working at PT ABC Airport's Yogyakarta Branch Office. Descriptive analysis was performed to identify respondent characteristics, such as age, gender, education stage, and years of service. The information revealed that the majority of workers are male, accounting for 83% or 57 individuals. In terms of age, the largest group of workers falls inside of the 32 to 35-year age range, representing 25% or 17 people. Regarding education, most workers hold a high school diploma, comprising 72% or 50 individuals. Additionally, the highest proportion of workers, 23%, get a tenure of service inside of a specific range, totaling 16 individuals.

Validity and Reliability Test

Figure 2. Outer Model

In this study, hypothesis testing was had by means of path coefficient bootstrapping inside of the SmartPLS framework. The evaluation process involved several critical criteria: the orientation of the original sample values, that delineates the direction of the impact; a p-value of ≤ 0.05 , that signifies statistical significance; and a t-statistic value exceeding 1.96, that corroborates the hypothesis acceptance. The composite reliability assessment, by Cronbach's Alpha values surpassing 0.70, validates that the information adheres to the prescribed standards for composite reliability. Additionally, the outcomes of the discriminant validity analysis, where all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are on top of 0.50, confirm that the information meets the requisite criteria for discriminant validity. As a outcome, the study information does get satisfied all the necessary instrument criteria, rendering it suitable for further analytical procedures. A comprehensive summary of the final outcomes from the instrument testing is presented below.

Table 2. Outer Model Output

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Job Insecurity	0.967	0.976	0.736
Job Stress	0.957	0.959	0.683
Turnover Intention	0.940	0.969	0.767
Digital Transformation	0.986	0.987	0.706

Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis testing in this study was executed utilizing path coefficient bootstrapping via SmartPLS. The evaluation was based on several criteria: the direction of the original sample values, that indicates the nature of the impact; a p-value of ≤ 0.05 , that establishes statistical significance; and a t-statistic greater than 1.96, that supports the validation of the hypothesis.

Table 3. Bootstrapping Output

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Job Insecurity → Turnover Intention	0,267	2.402	0,016
Job Stress → Turnover Intention	0,523	4.732	0,000
Digital Transformation x Job Insecurity → Turnover Intention	-0,407	3.140	0,002
Digital Transformation x Job Stress → Turnover Intention	0,223	2.201	0,028

1. The impact of job insecurity on turnover intention does get an Original Sample value of 0.267, a statistical t value of 2.402 > 1.96, and a P Value of 0.016 < 0.05. So, it can be summarized that Job Insecurity does get a noteworthy good impact on Turnover Intention, so H1 is accepted.
2. The impact of Job Stress on Turnover Intention does get an Original Sample value of 0.523, a statistical t value of 4.732 > 1.96, and a P Value of 0.000 < 0.05. So, it can be summarized that Job Stress does get a noteworthy good impact on Turnover Intention, so H2 is accepted.
3. The impact of Digital Transformation that moderates Job Insecurity on Turnover Intention does get an Original Sample value of -0.407, a statistical t value of 3.140 > 1.96, and a P Value of 0.002 < 0.05. So, it can be summarized that Digital Transformation moderates the noteworthy unfavorable connection among Job Insecurity and Turnover Intention, so H3 is rejected.
4. The impact of Digital Transformation that moderates Job Stress on Turnover Intention does get an Original Sample value of 0.223, a statistical t value of 2.201 > 1.96, and a P Value of 0.028 < 0.05. So, it can be summarized that Digital Transformation moderates the noteworthy good connection among Job Stress and Turnover Intention, so H4 is accepted.

DISCUSSION

1. Impact of job insecurity on turnover intention

Job insecurity is a situation where workers get unsafe when carrying out their duties and can cause tension at work. workers who get job insecurity will get uncertainty about their jobs and get worried about losing their jobs. This may be due to workers getting that their status is an outsourced worker so that the company may not continue the contract if there is a modify in company conditions. In addition, workers get that parts of the job such as salary, position, promotion, and a comfortable work environment are very important in influencing the stage of security and comfort of individuals in carrying out work. Until now, the company still uses a cost leadership policy or cost savings regarded to human resources, especially outsourced workers where the education that is recognized as the basis for calculating salaries is at the high school stage, although there are several workers whose last education is on top of that stage. Outsourced workers who realize that they only work according to the work contract that does get been made get thought about what if in the future they no longer work so that workers overcome this threat by looking for other alternative jobs that can provide job security for them. Thus, if the company no longer needs their labor, they can still fulfill their needs. This is handled by the outcomes of study had by Arnes et al. (2020) that indicates that job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on turnover intention and study had by Asdiltvira et al. Asdiltvira et al. (2023) that indicates that job insecurity does get a good and noteworthy impact on intention to stop working. However, the outcomes in this study do not support study by Azizah & Murniningsih (2022) that states that job insecurity does get a unfavorable and innoteworthy impact on turnover intention and study by Suwarsono et al. (2022) by the outcomes of job insecurity having a noteworthy unfavorable impact on turnover intention.

2. Impact of job stress on turnover intention

Workers often face task demands regarded to the volume of work that needs to be completed, leading to getings of exhaustion as they strive to finish their tasks. This situation is exacerbated when workers are required to take on additional workloads due to others leaving the company. When workers are assigned tasks that align by their skills and competencies, they tend to get satisfied and content by their work. However, if they are given tasks that exceed their capabilities or do not align by their expertise, it can outcome in noteworthy stress, leading to heightened stages of job-related anxiety. In addition, personal demands regarded to harmonious connections among workers can trigger work stress. Escalating job stress is likely to increase workers' propensity to leave their organization. This assertion is handled by the study of Asdiltvira et al. (2023), that indicates a noteworthy good connection among job stress and workers' intent to resign, thus underscoring the critical impact of stress on turnover intentions. However, the outcomes of this study diverge from the conclusions drawn by Anastasia et al. (2022), who identified a substantial unfavorable impact of job stress on turnover intention, as well as from Kurniawati & Surya (2022), who decided that job stress exerts an innoteworthy impact on workers' intent to leave their positions.

3. Impact of digital transformation on the connection among job insecurity and turnover intention

Outsourced workers often view digital transformation as a factor that enhances their job security. The introduction of new technologies is seen as a way to boost their ability to assess and improve their individual performance. Additionally, when digital transformation is implemented alongside specialized training programs and devoid of any reduction in staff due to automation, workers tend to get a more good view of these modifys. This is because the innovations introduced for digital transformation are regarded as tools that complement their work and enhance productivity. Furthermore, many outsourced workers are millennials, known for their talent and high stages of engagement. Consequently, when a company's digital innovation is coupled by a well-structured implementation strategy, workers are likely to perceive that the company is thriving, that can increase their sense of security and reassurance. These findings are consistent by the study had by Caselli et al. (2023), that demonstrates that the implementation of technological innovations inside of organizations correlates by a decrease in job insecurity among workers. For those who continue their employment post-innovation, these technological advancements are interpreted as signs of organizational robustness and enhanced internal communication. Dengler & Gundert (2021) decided that in Germany, the extent of job computerization unfavorably impacts workers' views of job security.

4. Impact of digital transformation on the connection among job stress and turnover intention

Outsourced workers at PT ABC Airport's Yogyakarta Branch Office perceive that the company's digital transformation may increase pressure, particularly concerning high targets and demanding tasks. This heightened pressure may stem from the absence of clear time and location boundaries due to digitalization, making workers get obligated to be constantly available to receive and respond to work-related tasks, even outside of regular working hours. As a outcome, workers often struggle to distinguish among work time and personal time for rest. Additionally, the stress can be exacerbated by the numerous information integration applications the company uses, that require extensive daily analysis of information and information. The proliferation of digital technologies—such as email, instant messaging, and social media—can generate an overwhelming amount of information that requires rapid processing. The strain outcomeing from the use of these digital tools in professional settings can get detrimental impacts on both workers and organizations, notably by exacerbating worker turnover. Previous investigations, including those by Makowska-Tłomak et al. (2023) and Azzahra et al. (2022), reveal that job stress arises from the need for workers to continually adapt and align their roles by ongoing digital transformation. Additionally, Ayumi & Murniati (2024) highlight that the stress induced by technological integration plays a crucial role in shaping workers' decisions about whether to remain by their current employer or explore alternative career options. Conversely, this study's findings contradict the conclusions drawn by Aydınli & Erkasap (2023), who reported that digital transformation does get a pronounced unfavorable impact on job stress. Their study posits that, under certain conditions, digital transformation can actually facilitate a better work-life balance and alleviate job-related stress, suggesting a more nuanced connection among technological advancements and worker well-being.

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